

Descriptive to assess knowledge and practice regarding selected antenatal care among primigravida mothers in view to develop information guide sheet in selected hospital Bareilly, (U.P.)

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Abstract

Introduction: Antenatal care is a vital component of maternal healthcare, encompassing a spectrum of interventions aimed at promoting the health and well-being of pregnant women and their unborn children. Through regular check-ups, screenings, and educational sessions, antenatal care aims to monitor the progress of pregnancy, detect and manage complications, and provide essential information and support to expectant mothers.

Objectives: To assess the knowledge regarding selected antenatal care among primigravida mothers. To assess the practice regarding selected antenatal care among primigravida mothers. To determine the association between knowledge and practice regarding selected antenatal care with their selected demographic variables. To correlate the knowledge and practice of selected antenatal care among primigravida mothers.

Material and Methods: A Descriptive research design, Pre – test Post – test was used to conduct the study at Rohilkhand Medical College and hospital, Bareilly. Non – Probability convenient sampling technique was used to select primigravida mother. Data was collected by using 20 YES/NO type of statement. 60 primigravida mothers selected for Pre and Post test. Educational intervention Booklet was used which need primigravida mother/How to perform care during antenatal period implemented through verbal discussion and explanation. Post- test was conducted after 7 to 10 days after intervention among both the groups. The average time to complete the session was 20 – 25 mins. Descriptive statistics include frequency, percentage, mean, mean difference, standard deviation was used to describe the result.

Conclusion: Antenatal affects the global health of individuals. Antenatal care its self-care activity and more important to carefully we can do it. It required mother activity, participation and motivation. Structured teaching program significantly increases the knowledge on antenatal care among first and second trimester primigravida mothers. So, in future nurses can prepare an effective structured teaching program to reduce the maternal mortality rate.

Keywords: Assess; Knowledge; Practice; Antenatal Care; Primigravida mothers

1. Introduction

Pregnancy and childbirth are special events in a woman's life. But during this period, they are more vulnerable to disease and death. Antenatal care is an umbrella term used to describe the medical procedures and care that are carried out during pregnancy. In promoting antenatal care, it is essential that the effectiveness of this service leaves no room for doubt. Antenatal care is named as one of the four pillars of the safe motherhood initiatives. The overall aim of antenatal care is to produce a healthy mother and baby at the end of pregnancy.

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Antenatal care is a vital component of maternal healthcare, encompassing a spectrum of interventions aimed at promoting the health and well-being of pregnant women and their unborn children. Through regular check-ups, screenings, and educational sessions, antenatal care aims to monitor the progress of pregnancy, detect and manage complications, and provide essential information and support to expectant mothers.

Antenatal care refers to pregnancy-related health care provided by a doctor or a health worker in medical facility or at home. Antenatal care should monitor a pregnancy for signs of complication detect and treat pre-existing and concurrent problems of pregnancy. It should also provide advice and counseling or preventive care, diet during pregnancy, delivery care, post-natal care and related issues. Antenatal care is necessary for ensuring a healthy mother and baby at the end of gestation. The antenatal period is a time of physical and psychological preparation of birth and parenthood. Becoming a parent is a time of intense learning both for parents and for those close to them.

Primigravida mothers, women experiencing their first pregnancy, represent a unique demographic group with specific needs and challenges during the antenatal period. As they embark on this journey for the first time, understanding their knowledge and practices regarding antenatal care is essential. Their adherence to recommended practices and their awareness of potential risks and interventions can significantly impact maternal and neonatal health outcomes. One of the most important components of antenatal care is to offer information and advice to women about pregnancy related complication and possible curative measures for early detection and management of complication.

1.1. Aim

To study the knowledge and practice regarding antenatal care among primigravida mothers with a view to develop information guide sheet.

1.2. Objectives

- To assess the knowledge regarding selected antenatal care among primigravida mothers.
- To assess the practice regarding selected antenatal care among primigravida mothers.
- To determine the association between knowledge and practice regarding selected antenatal care with their selected demographic variables.
- To correlate the knowledge and practice of selected antenatal care among primigravida mothers.

2. Materials and methods

- Research Approach: Descriptive Research Approach
- Research Design: Descriptive Research Design
- Setting of the study: Rohilkhand Medical College & Hospital, Bareilly.
- Population: Primigravida mothers in Rohilkhand Medical College & Hospital, Bareilly.
- Sample: primigravida mothers in Rohilkhand Medical College & Hospital, Bareilly
- Sampling Size: 60 primigravida mothers
- Sampling Technique: Non-probability convenient sampling technique

2.1. Inclusion criteria

- Primigravida mothers who will be present at the time of data collection.
- Primigravida mothers who are willing to participate

2.2. Exclusion criteria

- Primigravida mothers who will not be available at the time of data collection.
- Primigravida mothers who will not give concern to participate in study.

2.3. Variables of study

- Independent Variable: Educational intervention on tracheostomy care among staff nurses.
- Dependent Variable: Knowledge about tracheostomy care among staff nurses.

2.4. Description of Research Tool

- The tool consists of three parts, namely:
- Part 1: Socio-demographic data

- Part 2: Self-structured questionnaire
- Part 3: Self-structured checklist:

The structured questionnaire consists of two parts.

- *Part 1: Socio-demographic data*

It consists of 8 items regarding demographic information of the subject such as age, education, occupation, residential area of living, type of family, family income, trimester and previous knowledge about antenatal care.

Section A: Demographic Data includes Age, sex, marital status, Professional Education, Experience, have you ever provided tracheostomy care to patient, Tracheostomy care.

- *Part 2: Self-structured questionnaire*

It consists of 30 questions related to knowledge on antenatal care among primigravida mothers.

- *Part 3: Self-structured checklist*

It consists of 20 statements related to practice of antenatal care. In this part 2-point (yes or no) scale was included for the responses.

- *Data collection procedure*

The written permission was obtained from the Keshlata hospital, Bareilly. 60 primigravida mothers were selected by non-probability convenience sample technique. Self-introduction was given by investigators, and the purpose of the study was explained. The data was collected on 24 April 2025 to 02 May 2025. Data was collected by using perception scale and attitude scale.

3. Results

Table 1 Distribution of demographic variables

S. No.	Socio-Demographic variables	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age		
	≤ 20 years	20	33.33%
	21 - 25 years	16	26.66%
	26 - 35 years	14	23.33%
	36 years & above	10	16.66%
2.	Education		
	Informal	24	40%
	High school	12	20%
	Intermediate	16	26.66%
	Undergraduate & above	08	13.33%
3.	Occupation		
	Homemaker	24	40%
	Private job	20	33.33%
	Government job	10	16.66%
	Others/self-employment	06	10%
4.	Residential area of living		
	Rural	35	58.33%
	Urban	25	41.66%

5.	Type of family		
	Joint family	23	38.33%
	Nuclear family	22	36.66%
	Extended family	16	26.66%
6.	Family Income (per month in rupees)		
	< 10,000/-	16	26.66%
	10,001/- - 15,000/-	20	33.33%
	15,001/- - 20,000/-	18	30%
	>20,000/-	06	10%
7.	Trimester		
	I trimester	30	50%
	II trimester	18	30%
	III trimester	12	20%
8.	Previous knowledge about antenatal care		
	Yes	20	33.33%
	No.	40	66.66%

Table 2 Correlation between knowledge and practice regarding antenatal care among primigravida mothers. N= 60

Assessment	Mean	S.D.	Mean difference	R
Knowledge	24.4	4.15	16.6	0.34
Practice	7.8	2.02		

Table 3 Percentage distribution of knowledge regarding antenatal care among primigravida mothers.

Knowledge level	Frequency	Percentage
Poor	28	46.66%
Average	24	40%
Good	08	13.33

The above table represents that knowledge score 28 (46.66%) had poor knowledge, 24 (40%) had Average knowledge and 08(13.33%) had good knowledge.

Figure 1 Percentage Distribution of Knowledge Regarding Antenatal Care Among Primigravida Mothers

4. Discussion

The study identified inadequate knowledge regarding antenatal care among primigravida mothers, with 46.66% having poor knowledge and only 13.33% demonstrating good knowledge. Although utilization of antenatal services was satisfactory, reflected by regular antenatal visits (80%) and complete TT immunization (100%), several essential practices such as early registration, recognition of danger signs, timely anomaly scans, physical activity, and safe medication practices were poorly followed. Nutritional practices showed moderate adherence, particularly in supplement intake and hydration. No significant association or correlation was found between knowledge, practice, and socio-demographic variables. These findings emphasize the need for focused, practical, and behavior-oriented antenatal education for primigravida mothers.

5. Conclusion

Antenatal affects the global health of individuals. Antenatal care itself care activity and more importantly we can do it. It required mother activity, participation and motivation. Structured teaching program significantly increases the knowledge on antenatal care among first and second trimester primigravida mothers. So, in future nurses can prepare an effective structured teaching program to reduce the maternal mortality rate

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

- Research approval has taken from the institutional research committee. The present research work does not contain any studies performed on animal/ humans' subjects by any of the authors
- Permission was taken from the hospital before conducting the study and informed consent was obtained from all the participants included in the study.
- Prior to conducting the study, ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Bareilly International University.
- Permission was obtained from the Medical Superintendents of the selected hospitals.
- The data collection procedure was explained to the participants, and informed consent was obtained.
- Participants were assured that their data would be kept confidential and used solely for research purposes.
- Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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